

PACKAGING OF TOMATO PASTE PRODUCTS

Абдиева Г.М.

Head of the Department of Agricultural Product Storage, Cultivation and Processing Technology of the Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agro-Technology, Scientific Director.

Рзамбетов А.Р.

2nd year graduate student of Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agro-Technology.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13979615>

Abstract. Among the vegetables, tomato products, which are rich in minerals and vitamins, which the population eats in winter, occupy a special place. Its fruits are consumed fresh, preserved and processed. Currently, it is an important issue to save and process tomato fruits grown during the season and supply them to the population during the off-season.

Key words: tomato, heating, auger, jar, sorbic acid, sterilization, cooling, apparatus, aseptic cups.

УПАКОВКА ТОМАТНОЙ ПАСТЫ

Аннотация. Среди овощей особое место занимает томатная продукция, богатая минеральными веществами и витаминами, которую население употребляет в пищу в зимний период. Ее плоды употребляют в свежем виде, консервируют и перерабатывают. В настоящее время актуальным является вопрос сохранения и переработки плодов томата, выращенных в сезон, и поставки их населению в межсезонье.

Ключевые слова: томат, нагрев, шнек, банка, сорбиновая кислота, стерилизация, охлаждение, аппарат, асептические стаканы.

Introduction.

Tomato paste. The boiling temperature inside the tomato paste vacuum evaporation apparatus is not sufficient to kill microorganisms. After packaging, the tomato paste is heated to 850C if it is sterilized in the tray, and to 960C if the hot pouring method of canning is used.

For heating, periodically operating devices are used (VNIKOP-2 collecting-heating device), in which the product is held for 10-12 minutes. Continuous - shell-and-tube, screw, and tube heat exchangers are also used. Due to the high viscosity of tomato paste, they do not provide the desired heating effect.

Tomato paste is packed in iron, glass jars and aseptic bags under aseptic conditions. The filled cans are hermetically sealed, the product placed in containers up to 3 liters is sterilized at a temperature of 1000C for 15-50 minutes under a pressure of 100-150 kPa (depending on the size

and type of container) and cooled in water.

In addition to autoclaves, continuously operating rotor sterilizers-coolers are also used to sterilize tomato paste packed in No. 14 (3 l) iron cans.

Tomato paste can be canned by pouring it hot into jars No. 14 and 15. It is packed at a temperature of 92-950C, jars are closed, held for 20-25 minutes, and then cooled in water until the temperature is 50-600C.

Microorganisms are killed in tomato paste by heating it to 950C for 10 minutes. Their de-dusting is also achieved by high-temperature heating before steaming the pulp stream.

Cooling of iron cans No. 14 and No. 15 with tomato paste is carried out by immersing them in cold water or showering over them in continuously operating devices. If a thin film of cold water forms on the cooling jar, the cooling process will accelerate due to the evaporation of the water as a result of the rotation of the jar. After the hot product is placed in the jar, the water vapor in it condenses and creates a vacuum, and the jar undergoes a sharp deformation under the influence of atmospheric pressure. In order to prevent deformation of can No. 15, it is made of thick-walled (0.35 mm) tin. Five rows of stiffness ribs are made in the body of the jar. The relief of the bottom of the jar and the lid, when the difference between the pressures inside and outside the jar, these parts of the jar are drawn into the jar and the vacuum is slightly reduced. In addition to cans, varnished tins made of aluminum with a volume of 175 g are used for packaging. The tubes are filled with tomato paste at a temperature of 85-880C, and the open back is folded three times to seal it. Then the roots are cooled under a water shower, dried with hot air and placed in boxes.

They are stored at a temperature of 0-50C for up to 6 months.

Tomato paste is also packed in barrels with 10% table salt added as a preservative. This amount of salt stops the growth of microorganisms, but does not guarantee the preservation of the product. It is necessary to ensure a good sanitary condition of the product and the container, before packaging it should be heated and stored in warehouses with a temperature not higher than 150C.

Tomato paste and salt are mixed in equipment without copper details.

Tomato paste is packed in 100 kg barrels. They are treated sanitary, weighed and marked. Pouring is done through the spigot hole. This hole is then sealed with a wooden plug wrapped in parchment paper soaked in formalin.

When calculating the amount of tomato paste, the amount of salt is not added to the dry matter.

Salted tomato paste cannot be of high quality.

Preservatives are used when tomato paste is stored in non-hermetic containers. The amount of 0.025-0.05% of sorbic acid has a bactericidal effect on molds and yeasts. Bacterial spores do

not die under the influence of sorbic acid. Tomato paste should be heated to completely remove the seeds of microorganisms.

Difference in chemical composition of tomato paste and tomato puree

Table 1

T/P	Chemical composition	Tomato puree	Tomato paste
1	Dry matter	12	30
2	Nitrous oxide	1,9	4,8
4	Carbohydrates	7,6	19,0
5	Organic acids	1,0	2,5
6	Klechatka	0,4	1,0
7	Mineral substances	1,1	2,7

Consumption and energy value of 100 grams of tomato products

Table 2

Name of the product	Carbohydrates, g	Витамилар, мг				Energy value, kcal
		β- carotene	B ₁	PP	C	
<i>Tomato puree %:</i>						
12	7,1	—	—	—	—	37
15	8,9	—	—	—	—	46
20	11,8	1,8	0,05	0,6	26,0	65
<i>Tomato paste %:</i>						
25	15,8	—	—	—	—	79
30	19,0	2,0	0,15	1,9	45,0	99
35	22,2	—	—	—	—	111
40	25,3	—	—	—	—	127
<i>Salted tomato paste, %:</i>						
27						
32	17,1	—	—	—	—	88
37	20,3	—	—	—	—	102
	23,4	—	—	—	—	117
<i>Diluted tomato juice</i>	26,4	—	—	—	—	106

REFERENCES

1. Бўриев Х.Ч., Жўраев Р., Алимов О. Мева-сабзавотларни сақлаш ва дастлабки ишлов бериш. – Т.: Мехнат, 2002. б

2. Додаев Қ.О., Маматов И.М. Озиқ-овқат маҳсулотларини консервация корхоналарининг лойиҳалаш асослари ва технологик ҳисоблари (ўқув қўлланма). – Т.: Иқтисод-молия, 2006. 165 б
3. Драгилов А.И., Дроздов В.С. Технологические оборудование предприятий перерабатывающих отраслей АПК. – М.: Колос, 2001. 114 ст